

USE OF BLENDED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

Farmonov Sherzodbek Raxmonjonovich

Ferghana state university, Ferghana, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159196>

Abstract. *This article describes the advantages of using Blended Learning technology in organizing independent education for students in higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *Online learning platforms, personalized learning paths, access to resources, online discussions and forums, video conferencing, gamification, self-assessment and feedback, peer review, flexible scheduling, progress tracking, regular assessments, instructor support, integration of technology.*

Organizing independent education for students is a crucial aspect of fostering self-directed learning and helping students develop lifelong learning skills. Here are some steps and strategies to effectively organize and support students' independent education:

- **Clear learning objectives:** Start by defining clear and measurable learning objectives. Students need to know what they are expected to achieve during their independent learning journey.
- **Resource selection:** Provide students with a curated list of resources, including textbooks, articles, online courses, videos, and interactive learning materials. These resources should align with the learning objectives.
- **Online learning platforms:** Utilize online learning platforms or Learning Management Systems (LMS) where students can access educational content, submit assignments, and track their progress.
- **Customized learning paths:** Tailor learning paths to each student's needs and preferences. Offer choices in topics and resources, allowing students to explore areas of personal interest within the broader curriculum.
- **Scheduling and time management:** Encourage students to create study schedules that suit their individual lifestyles. Emphasize the importance of time management to ensure regular progress.
- **Regular check-ins:** Schedule periodic check-ins or meetings with students to monitor their progress, address questions, and provide guidance. These can be in-person or virtual meetings.
- **Peer learning:** Encourage peer-to-peer learning through group discussions, study groups, or collaborative projects. Students can learn from each other and support each other's progress.
- **Mentoring and support:** Assign mentors or advisors who can guide students, answer questions, and provide academic or career advice. These mentors can be teachers, older students, or professionals in the field.
- **Assessment and feedback:** Implement regular assessments, quizzes, assignments, or projects to gauge students' understanding and progress. Provide timely and constructive feedback to help them improve.
- **Goal setting:** Encourage students to set clear, achievable short-term and long-term goals. This helps them stay motivated and focused on their education.

- **Portfolio development:** Have students create a portfolio of their work and accomplishments. This can be a digital portfolio showcasing projects, papers, and achievements related to their independent learning.
 - **Resource management:** Teach students how to manage and organize their learning resources effectively. This includes note-taking, file management, and citation skills.
 - **Problem-solving skills:** Emphasize critical thinking, problem-solving, and research skills to help students become independent learners. Encourage them to seek solutions to problems on their own.
 - **Reflective practice:** Encourage students to regularly reflect on their learning experiences. They can write journals, blogs, or participate in discussions about what they have learned and how they have grown.
 - **Continuous evaluation:** Continuously evaluate and adjust the independent learning program based on student feedback and performance. Make improvements and adapt to changing needs.
 - **Parent and guardian involvement:** Keep parents and guardians informed about students' progress and encourage their support at home.
 - **Accessibility and inclusivity:** Ensure that all students have access to resources and support, including those with diverse learning needs.
 - **Promote lifelong learning:** Emphasize that independent learning is a skill that will serve students well beyond their formal education. Encourage a growth mindset and a love for learning.
- To achieve these goals, it is important to use Blended Learning technology. Blended Learning technology can play a significant role in organizing students' independent education within an organization. Here's how it can be effectively used:
1. **Online learning platforms:** Implement an online learning platform or Learning Management System (LMS) where students can access digital resources, such as video lectures, e-books, quizzes, and assignments. This allows them to engage with the material at their own pace and convenience.
 2. **Personalized learning paths:** Tailor the content to individual student needs and skill levels. With the help of data analytics and tracking tools, you can offer customized learning paths that align with each student's goals and areas of improvement.
 3. **Access to resources:** Provide students with access to a wide range of educational resources, including textbooks, articles, interactive simulations, and video tutorials. These resources can be accessed online, giving students the flexibility to explore topics of interest.
 4. **Online discussions and forums:** Create virtual discussion boards or forums where students can interact with peers and instructors. This fosters collaboration, peer-to-peer learning, and the exchange of ideas and information.
 5. **Video conferencing:** Use video conferencing tools for virtual office hours, one-on-one consultations, or group discussions. This allows students to have direct communication with instructors when they need clarification or guidance.
 6. **Gamification:** Incorporate gamification elements into the learning process to keep students engaged. Gamified activities, such as quizzes, challenges, and leaderboards, can make the learning experience more interactive and fun.

7. **Self-assessment and feedback:** Encourage students to self-assess their progress through regular quizzes, assignments, and self-evaluations. Provide prompt feedback to help them identify areas of improvement and track their growth.
8. **Peer review:** Use peer review assignments where students assess and provide feedback on each other's work. This not only reduces the instructor's workload but also encourages critical thinking and collaboration.
9. **Flexible scheduling:** Blended Learning allows students to choose when and where they learn. This flexibility is particularly useful for organizations where students have diverse schedules or commitments.
10. **Progress tracking:** Implement a system for tracking student progress. This could include dashboards that show their completion rates, scores on assessments, and areas where they may be struggling.
11. **Regular assessments:** Use periodic assessments to ensure students are meeting learning objectives. These assessments can be both online and offline and may include exams, presentations, or projects.
12. **Instructor support:** Even in independent learning environments, instructors play a crucial role. Make sure students have access to instructors for guidance, clarification, and support when needed.
13. **Integration of technology:** Ensure that the organization has the necessary technology infrastructure to support blended learning. This includes high-speed internet, computers, and access to relevant software and tools.
14. **Feedback mechanism:** Establish a feedback mechanism where students can express their concerns, suggest improvements, or report any technical issues. This helps in continually improving the blended learning program.

Blended Learning technology in the organization of students' independent education provides flexibility, personalization, and access to a wide range of resources, making it an effective approach for enhancing learning outcomes and student engagement. It allows students to take more ownership of their education while providing the necessary support and structure.

Conclusion. Organizing independent education for students requires careful planning, ongoing support, and a focus on developing students' self-motivation and self-regulation. By following these strategies, you can empower students to take ownership of their education and become lifelong learners.

REFERENCES

1. Shumilova N. N. Specificity of independent work / N. N. Shumilova / Specialist. - 2015. -№.: 10.- C. 16-17.
2. Shchukina G.I., Pedagogical problems of formation of cognitive interests of students / G.I. Schukin. - M.: Vldos, 2018. - 238 p.
3. Zimnyaya I.A., Pedagogical psychology: Textbook for universities / I.A. Zimnyaya. - M.: Lotos, 2019. - 249 p.
4. Farmonov Sh. R. Ta'lim jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish ahamiyati haqida. // “Informatika va axborot texnologiyalarining dolzarb muammolari” mavzusida Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari to‘plami – Termiz: Institut, 2023 y..- S. 35-37.

5. Farmonov Sh. R., Abdusalomova M.O. About the importance of cloud technologies// “Zamonaviy informatikaning dolzarb muammolari: o‘tmish tajribasi, istiqbollari” mavzusida Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari to‘plami – Toshkent: TDPU, 2023 y..- S. 30-34.
6. Фармонов, Ш., & Камбарова, Д. (2022). Как помочь ученикам развить интерес к учебе. O'rta Osiyo ta'lim va innovatsiyalar jurnali, 1(2), 118-120.